

The 30,000-foot view of Post Viral Syndrome

Letters to the Research Community – Entry 4

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In the late 1800s, medical specialties emerged with two primary goals: 1) augmentation of medical knowledge by allowing physicians to concentrate their observations on expanded numbers of similar cases and 2) increasing the efficiency of providing medical care to larger populations with similar medical conditions. (Weisz, 2003) Today, over 70% of physicians are classified as specialists. (“State of the Primary Care Workforce,” 2024) As specialists, we are trained to focus on specific areas or specific functions of the integrated organism we call human.

The same move toward specialty occurs in the sciences. We start with biology, general chemistry and basic physics. Specialization begins to occur before our bachelor’s degree and continues with increasing focus required as we advance through our graduate studies. Somewhere along the way, unless we specifically carve out time for our own general study or continuously collaborate, we inevitably lose sight of the “whole”.

As a specialized physician, I was acutely aware of my “boundaries”. When my practice shifted more and more to the care of “stuck” patients, I was forced to repeatedly cross these artificial boundaries. My patients had visited multiple specialties, often over decades, with no resolution. To even mention the word referral to them could result in their emotional shutdown. Over time, I realized these people had a “multi-specialty” presentation.

I am going to posit that post viral syndromes represent a “multi-specialty” presentation, both within the clinic and in the research lab. No one specialty will figure out the entire syndrome and no specialty will make as significant an inroad by themselves as they can make in a collaborative model. The solution requires us to leave our silos.

I spent the first 3 Entries in this series talking about heparan sulfate proteoglycans. I do think we will find them universally involved, whether they are functioning as expected or are disrupted by autoimmunity, genetics, or pathogen. Let’s put this complex system aside for now, though, and concentrate on establishing a systems model useful in analyzing post viral symptoms.

What do we see if we take a 30,000-foot view of the Post Viral Syndrome?

Close your eyes for a moment and paint your own picture. What do you imagine as you look down on the post viral syndrome landscape? The image that forms in your mind is likely shaped by your individual experiences, research and musings.

Since we learn from each other I'll share what I see. If you want to reach out and share your picture, then I can learn from you. We take steps toward collaboration through the sharing of ideas.

My first step in creating my personal model is to establish large categories for the type of systems that can be involved. I've come up with three categories that work for me.

The first category is easy to understand because it holds the systems that reside in other organisms, specifically the microbes involved in post viral response. In step 2, I'll end up splitting this group into pathogens and resident human microbiomes.

The second two categories were more difficult for me but I find their separation helpful for understanding what impacts them, how that might relate to pathology and how much effort it could take to affect change. Those two categories are 1) anticipatory systems and 2) non-anticipatory systems.

Anticipatory systems, as defined by theoretical biologist Robert Rosen, use internal predictive models when presented with a stimulus. (Louie, 2010; Rosen, 1985) These models anticipate what eventual need or harm may result from the current stimulus or stimuli. These systems respond, often rapidly, to what they predict will happen, not specifically to what is happening in the moment. Critically, the system acts on its model's predictions whether or not those predictions accurately reflect reality. (Deans, 2021) Interestingly, we can use different stimuli to temporarily alter anticipatory system responses; however, these systems tend to resume their reliance on their predictive models over time. What does it take to actually break the predictive model? Musings perhaps for another day.

Non-anticipatory systems are primarily reactive, responding only to current stimuli without prediction of future consequence. Non-anticipatory systems include most metabolic, regulatory and homeostatic systems. These systems often have baseline functions, initial protection strategies, feedback loops - even feed forward loops. Non-anticipatory systems can feed data to anticipatory systems.

A distinguishing factor between these two types of systems is the ease of changing non-anticipatory systems by a single or small collection of events. That makes these systems easier to analyze, easier to manipulate and easier to "fix". As scientists, we are more familiar and comfortable using reductivism in our study of non-anticipatory, reactive systems. To appreciate anticipatory systems will require expanding our scope to appreciate all the players in a more complex system.

Why do I want to tackle a complex idea like “anticipatory systems”? Because I think the concept is going to allow us a new way to frame post exertional malaise. This distinction will also help us work Circadian rhythms into our post viral syndrome research.

Now I have my 3 Level 1 categories:

- 1) Microorganisms
- 2) Anticipatory Systems
- 3) Non-Anticipatory Systems

Let’s break these 3 groups down into their major components, recognizing that we have the flexibility to add or subtract members of each category as we evaluate relevance in post viral sequelae.

- 1) Microorganisms
 - a. Pathogens
 - b. Host Microbiome
- 2) Anticipatory Systems
 - a. Central Governor
 - b. Circadian Clock
- 3) Non-Anticipatory Systems
 - a. Cellular/Energy Metabolism System
 - b. Autonomic System
 - c. Immune System
 - d. Cardiopulmonary System
 - e. Circulatory/Lymphatics System
 - f. Neuroendocrine System
 - g. GI/GU System

Now that we have our basic categories, we can establish a model that will allow us classify Post Viral Sequelae and create connectors between the categories.

Taking our Level 1 and Level 2 categories, our model template might look something like this:

Let's add a fairly common but "relatively simple" post SARS-CoV-2 presentation that affects multiple systems: dysosmia/anosmia. [Note: SARS-CoV-2 is not the first virus to cause a similar disruption of the olfactory system.](Asghari et al., 2025; Moran et al., 1992)

Post viral patients often complain of changes in or loss of their ability to smell – perhaps a result of direct viral invasion or consequence of immune response or both? Change in smell affects sense of taste, secretory response to food, changes in emotional response to situations, potential alterations in sleep, and can be quite dangerous (patients can't smell food gone bad, or gas leaks, or materials burning, ...).

At a minimum, the change impacts the following systems: autonomic, neuroendocrine, immune, and GI/GU. In addition, we realize there is a bilateral connection between olfaction and the circadian clock. Smell also may have a modifying effect on the central governor.

We can demonstrate those connections on our model as follows:

It is not imperative that we record a complete (I've left off the initiating mechanism for now) and totally accurate model on the first go. Show uncertainties with dashed lines. Create a reference key. This is a dynamic worksheet - perhaps a large worksheet of your model, or mine, or some combination thereof. Place it on the wall where teams can doodle, erase, color code, ponder, engage in group discussion. Display multiple models, one for each team member or subgroup. If you need to start over, consider creating a research archive of those replaced.

As we add additional signs and symptoms to our model, we may begin to see groupings that inspire us to look for associations or help us identify subgroups of post-viral patients. A missing connection may become obvious or we may recognize a pattern where one damaged function is repetitively associated with another. Our model becomes a pattern-detection tool – a chance for our right brain to establish patterns and flows that guide our left brain's focus in determining cause and effect.

With our basic modeling and categories established, we can now move toward tackling some of the complex, multi-system complaints common in post viral syndrome patients. We will likely revisit olfaction at some later date.

Soon we will take a fresh look at some of the more troubling post viral sequelae: including post exertional malaise and dysautonomia.

Until next time - kpm

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